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CLIMATE RESILIENT AND ENVIRONMENTALLY
SUSTAINABLE TRANSPORT INFRASTRUCTURE,
WITH A FOCUS ON INLAND WATERWAYS

D3.3 Tools for synchronodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparations

**CRISTAL - Climate resilient and environmentally sustainable transport
infrastructure, with a focus on inland waterways**

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation/Term	Description
AIPo	Agenzia Interregionale per il fiume Po
AJAX	Asynchronous JavaScript And XML
API	Application Programming Interface
ARIA	Accessible Rich Internet Applications
CEF	Connecting Europe Facility
CEMT	European Conference of Ministers of Transport
CERTH	Centre for Research & Technology Hellas
CI/CD	Continuous Integration/Continuous Delivery
DOM	Document Object Model
ETA	Estimated Time of Arrival
EAA	European Accessibility Act
EU	European Union
EuRIS	European River Information Services
FENIX	European FEderated Network of Information eXchange in LogistiX
HTML	Hypertext Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
IMO	International Maritime Organization
IV	Infrastrutture Venete
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JAWS	Job Access With Speech
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
IWW	Inland Water Ways
NVDA	NonVisual Desktop Access
NtS	Notices to Skippers
ORM	Object Relational Mapping
O-D	Origin-Destination

PHP	Hypertext Preprocessor
PGWWP	Państwowe Gospodarstwo Wodne Wody Polskie
REST	Representational State Transfer
POUR	Perceivable, Operable, Understandable, and Robust
SCMS	Syncho-modal Corridor Management System
SPA	Single Page Application
SEO	Search engine Optimization
SIR	Subsurface Inspection Radar
SNL	Service de la Navigation Luxemburg
UAT	User Acceptance Testing
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
VNF	Voies navigables de France
WP	Work Package
WSB	Wasserstraßen und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes
WCAG	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
XML	Extensible Markup Language

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1. Executive Summary

The present deliverable outlines the first functional implementation of CRISTAL's digital toolbox designed to support synchromodal transport planning and real-time decision-making under uncertainty. The Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS) is a key technological outcome of WP3 aiming to improve the resilience, efficiency, and environmental sustainability of IWT across Europe.

It integrates outputs from previous CRISTAL activities, particularly the software requirements (D2.1), architectural design (D3.1), and navigability and disruption alert research (D5.1). The system combines predictive analytics, dynamic route optimization, and real-time monitoring capabilities to respond proactively to disruptions like low water levels, lock failures, climate-induced events, thus ensuring continuity and reliability of multimodal transport chains.

This deliverable is informed by stakeholder engagement and training workshops carried out with pilot site partners in Italy, France, and Poland. Then, the early detection system for alerts is presented, which informs SCMS users about possible navigability issue during the route that they have chosen to carry out, as well how these navigability alerts are sourced and processed.

The synchromodal route planning system is detailed by focusing on Pilot rivers' vessel network determination, the development of key algorithms for route planning and re-planning, together with navigability alert processing.

The use and development of additional services for ETA and CO₂ optimization, Track & Trace and Smart Bulletin are described along with their compliance with the FENIX classification of digital services, completing the suite of decision support toolbox & services of the SCMS platform, eventually achieving real-time operations management.

Building upon the D3.1, the main software architecture details are presented along with the whole technology stack that was used to bring the SCMS platform in life. In-depth details are given for the synchromodal route planning algorithm, as well as for the synchromodal re-planning algorithm. After the software architecture was laid out, rigorous testing was carried out to ensure the developed tools are functional not only in software, but also in user level. The SCMS platform and its functionalities can be accessed through the following URL: <https://scms.imet.gr/>

A usage tutorial is presented so that both existing and future users of the SCMS get a complete understanding of how to effectively utilize the developed tools. The use cases for those tools are identified, along with the appropriate user personas that were defined for effectively designing the user interfaces and the overall user experience of the SCMS synchromodal tools, taking also into account the accessibility aspect.

Finally, some remarks are made about challenges and risks related to data gathering & digitalization, but also during the software development process.

This deliverable represents a foundation for iterative enhancement in subsequent releases (D3.4 and D3.5), where functionalities will be extended and validated through pilot demonstrations, contributing directly to CRISTAL's core objective of increasing IWT modal share and climate resilience.

1.1. Introduction

Inland Waterway Transport (IWT) represents a strategic mode of freight transport across Europe, offering a sustainable and scalable alternative to road transport. However, its widespread adoption continues to face operational and environmental challenges, especially in the context of climate-induced disruptions, infrastructure variability and fragmented digital coordination.

Work Package 3 (WP3) addresses these challenges by designing the Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS), a digital toolbox that enhances the resilience, efficiency and real-time adaptability of synchromodal transport corridors. The SCMS' functionalities are developed and integrated to the main system, so that it becomes a modular platform that combines predictive alerts for natural or human-caused river navigability disruptions, multimodal planning algorithms for optimal route selection and a dedicated action toolbox that provides operational decision-support services.

More specifically, three main groups of functionalities and tools were developed to support the SCMS' role in enhancing the efficient planning and management of the synchromodal passenger and freight operations across the designated transport networks. The first is the Early Detection & Information service, which collects and presents data from CRISTAL project partners, including river infrastructure managers (VNF, AIPo, IV) and technical solution providers (Fraunhofer), as well as from external systems such as EuRIS. This information is made available to SCMS users (e.g., LSPs, barge operators) to support their decision-making process. The second is the Disruption Impact Estimation service, which develops synchromodal planning and re-planning tools that consider existing and forecasted disruptions in the pilot rivers. These tools assess the feasibility of planned river routes and propose alternative transport options based on current and future river conditions. Lastly, the third group of functionalities, the Action Toolbox of services, is a set of digital tools for real-time operations management and decision support. It includes services such as Track & Trace, ETA Calculation and the Smart Bulletin, all of which follow the FENIX service architecture to ensure digital interoperability. The SCMS platform and its functionalities can be accessed through the following URL: <https://scms.imet.gr/>

In general, this deliverable reflects the outcome of co-development efforts among CRISTAL partners and pilot stakeholders in Italy, France, and Poland. It presents the technical developments, functionalities and interfaces of the SCMS, both at the functional and software development levels, and lays the foundation for its demonstration and validation.

1.2. Mapping CRISTAL outputs

This section provides an overview of the alignment of the document to the formal deliverable & corresponding task descriptions included in the GA and thus help the deliverable owners and the reviewers to conclude on the level of achievement of the deliverable/task goals.

Table 1 Alignment of DX.X contents to the corresponding GA deliverable & task(s) descriptions

CRISTAL GA Component Title	CRISTAL GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
<i>D3.3 Tools for synchromodal resource planning and cooperative operations preparations</i>	<i>D3.3. will develop tools and systems for synchro-modal resource planning and cooperative operations preparation.</i>	<i>Chapters 2,3,4 and 5</i>	<i>In these chapters, the approach and development of the three main functionalities are detailed along with the corresponding software architecture elements</i>
TASKS			
<i>Task 3.3/ Subtask 3.3.1 Early detection systems and alerts</i>	<i>RIS platforms in the project pilots are empowered with indicators and alerts on navigability quality, infrastructure conditions, and long-term climate variation. Data availability for barge operators and asset managers supports decision-making in normal and crisis situations, as well as mitigation and adaptation planning. Real-time data from flood monitoring and early-warning systems support preventive actions and emergency management. Climate indicators from projected scenarios inform long-term water-level estimation. Sensor-based data on flood-defence conditions enable continuous monitoring, preventive maintenance, and damage assessment during extreme events.</i>	<i>Chapter 2</i>	<i>Chapter 3 presents the selected approach and method for collecting disruption data to support early warning and decision-making for both operations and preventive maintenance. It provides information from the project's sensor systems, which offer early warning for infrastructure disruptions as well as navigability issues that may arise from extreme events. To this end, it also describes the integration of relevant data from existing operational systems (EURIS).</i>

<p>Task 3.3/ Subtask 3.3.2 Synchromodal planning system under uncertainty</p>	<p><i>Synchromodal planning tools are optimized and adapted to the requirements of IWT&L network systems management, utilizing state-of-the-art algorithms for disruptive events detection, dynamic route re-planning and mode-free booking. The tools will prioritize different features to suggest transport alternatives based on time, cost, service availability, as well as environmental-related ones. Emphasis will be given on the coordination of networks of supply chains, the bundling of flows, flexible/seamless modal-shift and integration/ interoperability in data sharing among systems and platforms.</i></p>	<p>Chapter 3</p>	<p><i>Chapter 4 provides details of the functionalities developed to exploit the collected disruption information in order to assess the feasibility of planned river routes. It also describes the functionality for presenting alternative transport modes in case a river route is not feasible, providing the necessary visibility for the dynamic -planning of operations and enabling a seamless modal shift and a synchromodal approach along the transport corridors.</i></p>
<p>Task 3.3/ Subtask 3.3.3 Real-time operations management and decision support toolbox & services</p>	<p><i>An inventory for dynamic planning and optimization tools & services (track and trace, ETA, dynamic routing); emissions, traffic and weather monitoring tools; e-documentation services e.tc. that have been either developed within CRISTAL project or were already available by past European projects. The toolbox will follow the principles set by past European projects (CEF FENIX) and its development will be based on the FENIX's Broker technology while the services' interface will follow the classification of digital services developed by FENIX.</i></p>	<p>Chapter 4</p>	<p><i>Chapter 5 details the development of additional services created based on specific pilot site requirements to support dynamic planning and optimization. It also covers the interoperability and connectivity of these services in accordance with the FENIX classification of digital services.</i></p>

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The present report is divided into nine chapters. The first chapter includes the executive summary along with the introductory section, the description of the document structure and the justification of the document alignment to the GA requirements. In the second chapter, the early detection system and alerts service is presented, which informs SCMS users about possible navigability issue during the route that they have chosen to carry out. The third chapter presents the developed synchro-modal planning system under uncertainty, and how this helps route planning decision support. In the fourth chapter, the real-time operations management and decision support toolbox & services are defined and described. In the fifth chapter, the software architecture and development efforts are outlined for the aforementioned services. The sixth chapter is dedicated to testing practices used for the developed software. In the seventh chapter, a SCMS usage tutorial is presented, along with user-related considerations like user personals and accessibility. The eighth chapter is about detailing risk challenges faced and how they were resolved. Finally, the ninth chapter includes the main conclusions that emerged from the work performed in Task 3.3 and describes the future steps for the development of the SCMS.

2. Early detection system and alerting service

2.1. Short description

This SCMS functionality consolidates forecasted disruption impacts on Inland Waterways (IWW) operations, by receiving structured data from various data sources, mainly from project partners, but also from existing external sources and legacy systems as well through REST API interfaces predefined JSON request body form. The nature of this data can range from forecasted water level alerts, extreme weather events and steep variations of climate conditions to public/social activities like strikes and failures of structural conditions on the infrastructure of the rivers.

All this consolidated information is made available to the SCMS users upon request through the Early Detection & Info Service page (Figure 1). Users can select the river to get relevant navigability alerts for, the alerts sender authority or organization, and a specific period during which the matched alerts would be effective.

More specifically, the user can select the river of interest and the source of information (e.g. Figure 1, in the Italian pilot case, AIPo, Infrastructure Venette and the Digital twins) to receive daily updates on the available alerting information.

Figure 1 Disruption information for the Italian pilot in river Po & the Canal as presented in the SCMS platform for a user-defined time period

Complementing the Early Detection & Info Service page, a configurable push notification service is also implemented inside “My Company” page, to disseminate relevant updates to registered stakeholders, leveraging user-defined preference profiles related to the rivers selected that would trigger those notifications, to ensure targeted and context-specific information delivery.

Figure 2 Alerts notifications configuration inside My Company page

2.2. Navigability alerts data sources

The SCMS page Early Detection & Info Service can give users valuable information about all kinds of navigability disruptions on the pilot rivers in the context of the CRISTAL project. Those disruptions alerts derive from various sources that differ according to the pilot case, where each can be examined separately.

In the Italian pilot case and the Po River, the navigability alerts data sources include two types of alerts. The first is related to expected operational disruptions due to possible failures in the metallic doors of locks, as these emerge from the analysis of data that comes from the implementation of the Acoustics Emission (AE) system. The information about these disruptions feeds the Digital Twin implemented by Fraunhofer to generate forecasts about the closure of the river’s locks and eventually the possibility of navigating the river according to the existing historical data gathered via the AE system. The second is related to expected changes in the navigable depth of the river Po outside the predefined limits based on the river vessels compatibility class, due to draught or floods, as these emerge from the analysis of historical and daily data from sensors implemented along the entire navigable part of the river. These changes are published daily and communicated to the SCMS from a dedicated system developed by AIPO and IV that provides the SCMS with NtS of many types of disruptions that may affect the river operations to ultimately be shown in the page.

In the French pilot case and the Seine and Moselle rivers, the navigability alerts data sources are of 3 main types. The first is about operational and maintenance issues - interior cavities or sub-cavities, internal erosion and interior water flows - of critical IWW infrastructure, mainly locks, that are identified via land-based and vessel-mounted Subsurface Inspection Radar (SIR) technology. The second is related to the Smart Buoys that are installed on the pilot rivers and used for flood management, as they can

automatically detect changes of their original anchorage location and send out this information to barge skippers, barge companies and freight forwarders for optimal cargo management and route planning. The information about both the infrastructure maintenance planning and the flood management use of smart buoys feed the Fraunhofer Digital Twin to generate forecasts about the closure of the river's locks and eventually the possibility of navigating the river. The DT also can emit alerts about the change of the Smart Buoys place of anchorage that feeds the SCMS. The third is related to various disruptions in the rivers Seine and Moselle in the form of NtS by utilizing the public and ArcGIS-emulated REST APIs of the EuRIS service [24]. The NtS messages limitations type could be of various natures: from available water depth, blockages and bridge heights clearances to restricted ability of mooring and berthing, speed limits and even non-restrictive but purely informative messages so that the skippers are aware of the whole context of their voyage. These changes are published throughout the whole course of each day every day and a specific software component of the SCMS that runs code scripts jobs fetches those NtS.

In the Polish pilot and the Vistula River, the navigability alerts data sources are pretty like the French pilot ones. Again, there are alerts available to the SCMS by Fraunhofer APIs that return forecasted lock closures in the river. The Smart Buoy System plays a critical role in this case as well, since it can measure water depths, ice sheet cover thickness and the change of their anchorage position. Lastly, the SCMS has established a semi-dynamic communication with University of Gdansk via documents available online that contain all information regarding newly published NtS by regional Polish Water Management authorities.

The relationship between the existing data sources and the pilots' rivers can be summarized in the table below.

Table 2 Table of correspondence between data sources and pilot rivers

River/Data source	DT locks status forecasts	DT buoy alerts	AIPo + IV NtS	EuRIS NtS (VNF, WSB, SNL)	PGWWP NtS
Po	X		X		
Seine	X	X		X	
Moselle	X	X		X	
Vistula	X	X			X

2.3. Data usage inside the SCMS

Evidently, the SCMS has access to a lot of data sources and the data that these make available to it. This data needs to be ingested, processed and presented properly in the user interface of Early Detection & Info Service page. There are 2 main ways that SCMS has access to them.

The first one is by publishing implemented REST API interfaces that "listen" to data transfers from other systems/API clients. SCMS is an application made with Laravel, a full-stack PHP programming language

web framework. To publish such REST APIs, specific API routes can be defined in the appropriate routes' declaration file of the application so that they become available to the appropriate API clients/data senders. Such data is the Smart Buoy System's alerts sent by the Fraunhofer Digital both for French and Polish pilots and the NtS and Smart Bulletin information sent by AIPo and IV.

The second way is the inverse of the first. It is done by implementing code scripts jobs that fetch from third-party REST APIs or other sources the data themselves. More specifically, Laravel Console Commands are created with PHP and scheduled to be executed at specific time intervals (cronjobs) that when executed, they make HTTP requests to appropriate project partners'/third-party APIs to fetch the needed data. Such data is the Polish NtS and the EurIS NtS.

After receiving the needed data one way or another, the next step is to process them by cleansing and validating their type and form while cherry-picking the appropriate fields to be stored in the SCMS main application database. Alerts are never deleted from the SCMS database; they are always available and maintained to ensure historical traceability and support retrospective and metrics/KPIs analysis.

The final step is the presentation of the alerts data to the users. Laravel controllers are responsible for retrieving alert data from the SCMS relational database tables. These controllers pass the data to Blade templating engine HTML templates, which render the user interface. Within these templates, users can interact with input controls to specify their preferences and dynamically display the relevant data in a summary table or even view them in a dedicated interactive map.

Figure 3 Overview of the navigability alerts data processing workflow

3. Synchromodal planning system under uncertainty

3.1. Short description

This functionality enables a comprehensive assessment of the impact of disruptions on logistics operations by leveraging both existing navigability disruption alerts and forecasted disruption data from the Digital Twin developed by Fraunhofer. It supports user-initiated requests to evaluate the feasibility of planned transport routes, considering current and anticipated network conditions (5).

The screenshot displays a web-based interface for route assessment, divided into three main sections:

- Select River:** A horizontal menu with four buttons: "Po" (highlighted in blue), "Seine", "Moselle", and "Vistula".
- Origin - Destination:** A panel with the following elements:
 - Section: "Select Origin-Destination Ports:"
 - Radio buttons for "Manually" and "Automatically" (checked).
 - A blue button: "Choose Point on Map and Calculate the Departure Port".
 - A dropdown menu showing "Porto di Cremona".
 - A dropdown menu showing "Porto di Valdaro".
- Vessel:** A panel with the following elements:
 - Section: "River Class Compatibility".
 - A dropdown menu showing "Class III".
 - Text: "Not every type of vessel can navigate all parts of the river."
 - Section: "Cargo Type".
 - A dropdown menu showing "Dry Bulk".
 - Section: "Cargo in Tons".
 - A dropdown menu showing "175".
 - Buttons at the bottom: "Vessel Network" (blue) and "Show the Shortest Route" (green).

To the right of the "Origin - Destination" and "Vessel" panels is a map showing a red route connecting the origin and destination ports across a river network.

Figure 4 Selection of O-D, vessel type and cargo characteristics for the route assessment

Additionally, the platform provides detailed insights, including CO₂ emission estimation, estimated time of arrival (ETA), and specific information about the nature and origin of disruptions (if any) along planned routes, thus enhancing operational planning, risk mitigation, and sustainability monitoring (Figure 4).

Figure 5 Example of a (feasible) route assessment result

It also provides visibility to the alternative modes routes that can be used to complement or substitute the assessed river routes, supporting dynamic mode shifts in response to disruptions or changing conditions according to the synchro-modality principles. These results are made available to the system user through the system's dashboard (Figure 5 and Figure 6).

Figure 6 Example of a (non-feasible) route assessment result with the relevant disruption information

Figure 7 Example of rail and road alternatives to the planned river route.

The mode-free booking implementation was not feasible due to the lack of accessible and structured booking data across transport modes. For now, users are encouraged to manually search for booking information such as train schedules or barge availability through their own or external sources on the countries and cities of the pilot rivers. This ensures that users can still make informed decisions, albeit with reduced automation and integration. Looking ahead, future iterations of the SCMS could incorporate mode-free booking functionality by establishing data-sharing agreements with transport operators, integrating open APIs, or leveraging real-time data feeds from public and private mobility platforms. These enhancements would significantly improve the system’s ability to offer seamless, automated, and user-centric transport planning.

3.2. River vessel network

The SCMS Disruption Impact Estimation page integrates a specialized vessel network visualization tool designed to support the synchro-modal route planning under uncertainty. When users activate the "Vessel Network" button, the system displays an interactive map highlighting the navigable segments of a selected river. These segments are classified according to the Classification of European Inland Waterways (CEMT) standards, allowing users to filter and view navigable river waterways by their

navigability class, which plays a crucial role in filtering navigable river segments. The vessel network is displayed as a separate map layer in brown colour and has a dedicated toggle button that when clicked, the visibility of the vessel network layer is toggled visible or not as shown in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Display of the navigable Vessel Network for CEMT Class III on River Vistula of the Polish pilot

Upon selection, the chosen class is transmitted to the backend system where vessel specifications associated with that CEMT class (e.g. length, width, draft, overhead clearance) are already stored. These specifications are then programmatically compared against the technical attributes of each river section, including minimum lock width, minimum lock depth, minimum bridge overhead clearance and minimum lock length. Only those river segments that meet or exceed the minimum required thresholds for the selected vessel class are returned and visualized on the interactive map. This ensures that users are presented with accurate, class-compliant navigability data, which is essential for reliable synchro-modal route planning, especially under uncertain or disrupted conditions.

3.3. Route planning

In the Route Assessment step of Disruption Impact Estimation page, users can input the key parameters of departure time and vessel speed (in km/h) to initiate a route planning assessment. The system then evaluates the feasibility of IWT routes, considering both current navigability alerts and forecasted disruptions derived from the Digital Twin. In addition to navigability, the system provides detailed insights into each proposed route, including Estimated Time of Arrival (ETA), CO₂ emissions estimation, disruption origin and nature and alternative routing via road or rail, if applicable.

Diving more into the technical parts of this module and what it does behind the scenes, it enables intelligent multimodal transport planning by assessing the feasibility of inland waterway navigation between two ports, taking into account vessel characteristics (from the river class compatibility selection input) and infrastructure limitations such as lock dimensions, bridge clearances, and water depth. It also integrates real-time river alerts to enhance safety and operational awareness. The system outputs

structured data including route durations, geospatial representations, port sequences and environmental indicators, supporting data-driven decision-making for logistics operators, infrastructure managers, and policy makers. This functionality contributes to the broader goals of promoting modal shift, enhancing transport resilience and supporting sustainable urban and regional logistics within the European transport ecosystem.

3.4. Disruptive events detection

When the user provides the crucial parameters of departure time and vessel speed, the system uses those inputs to process real-time, existing, forecasted disruption alerts and predictive insights from the Digital Twin, to assess route feasibility. On system level and according to the data modelling that has been implemented in the SCMS database and ORM system, the following data are used to detect disruptive events that would affect an IWW route navigability:

- Smarty buoy alerts
- Lock statuses
- Notices to Skippers
- Water level forecasts

The route planning algorithm dynamically identifies viable waterway routes by evaluating the information gathered from checking the above data, and in cases where segments are non-navigable due to disruptions, it generates alternative IWW routes by excluding problematic sections.

3.5. Synchro-modal route re-planning

If the route planning algorithm determines that there is no feasible river route to follow, given the parameters the user supplied, it then tries to calculate an alternative river route that would be either from a different branch of the main river or from a canal that may also exist in the river.

In addition, it calculates a road transport alternative using external routing services, specifically the Google Maps API, providing estimated travel times and geospatial data for comparative analysis. Furthermore, it evaluates rail transport as an option, identifying the most efficient rail connection from intermediate ports to the final destination and estimating environmental impact through CO₂ emission calculations based on cargo weight and distance. Below, a flowchart with the complete algorithm for the route planning and re-planning with the alternative routes is presented for better clarity of the whole process followed on code level inside the backend system of the SCMS.

Figure 9 Flowchart of the process followed for IWT synchro-modal planning and re-planning

4. Real-time operations management and decision support toolbox & services

This functionality includes a modular toolbox of value-added services, customized to the specific requirements of each inland waterway corridor. All tools of the “Action toolbox of services” aim to enhance situational awareness and thus operational efficiency of the inland navigation system of the river systems where they are implemented. The system architecture allows for the addition of more services in the future if requested.

4.1. Track & Trace

The Track and Trace tool is a dashboard developed for the Vistula River to support voyage testing and provide real-time positioning of operating barges (Figure 10).

Figure 10 Example of the Track & Trace functionality in the Vistula river

CERTH has developed a public REST API that requires authentication and is developed specifically for receiving Smart Buoy System data related to the location of the vessels en route in the Polish pilot rivers. Smart buoys transmit each travelling vessel’s GPS coordinates, the timestamp of the data transmission

and the identification number of the vessel in JSON format. This information is saved in the SCMS database and after that is automatically presented to the user inside the Track & Trace page as a pulsing dot inside an interactive map that points the vessel's location. The vessel's location is updated in real-time inside the page if a new Smart Buoy vessel location data transmission happens with the use of Laravel server-side emitted events and the Websockets real-time communication protocol, allowing for real-time vessel location visibility at all stages of the vessel voyage.

4.2. ETA optimization

The ETA optimization tool is a dashboard that was developed by CERTH for all river pilots, for calculating the ETA of the optimal river route for a specific origin and destination, using as input (from the system user) the average vessel speed and the average delay on the locks along the route (Figure 11).

ETA Calculation
Calculates the route with the optimal Estimated Time of Arrival, taking into account the average delay in Locks.

1 Select River

PO
SEINE
MOSELLE
VISTULA

2 Vessel

Class: Class III

Speed in km per hour: 10

Check vessel compatibility with the river.

3 Select Route

Departure Port: Porto di Cremona

Destination Port: Porto di Valdaro

Average Delay in Locks: 00:30

Default average delay in the Fairway, can be updated if needed.

Vessel Network
ETA Optimal Route

Optimal route calculation based on vessel & per lock delay

FROM	TO	TIME
Porto di Cremona	Sacchetta	12 hours 51 minutes
Sacchetta	Casale	00 hours 48 minutes
Casale	Porto di Valdaro	01 hours 06 minutes
Total Time		14 hours 45 minutes

The map shows the optimal route (red line) connecting Porto di Cremona to Porto di Valdaro, passing through Sacchetta and Casale. The map also displays the vessel network (blue lines) and the selected river (orange line).

Figure 11 Example of ETA calculation, considering average speed and lock delays

In this tool, the optimal route is calculated by means of the shortest ETA, while also considering a user-defined average delay at all the locks that a vessel might pass through its voyage on the river. No alerts are considered, and there is also the possibility of displaying the vessel network of the selected river class, like in the Disruption Impact Estimation dashboard.

4.3. Smart Bulletin

The Smart Bulletin is a dashboard with forecasted river navigability maps, which is the graphic representation of the Smart Bulletin developed in the context of the Italian pilot activities (Figure 12). Using this tool, the user can select the time period of his interest along with the vessel class he intends to use, and the system displays the forecasted navigability status (green – navigable, red – non navigable) in all segments of the river Po and the Canal for the specific vessel class. This time period can be extended up to 2 weeks from the current date.

Figure 12 The Smart Bulletin dashboard for river Po and the Canal.

CERTH has developed a public REST API that requires authentication and is developed specifically for receiving forecasted Smart Bulletin-water level depth data for the river Po of the Italian pilot by AIPo. The Smart Bulletin data include the forecasted water levels for 7 days, along with the eligibility for navigation of each of the seven CEMT classes. This information is saved in the SCMS database and is ready for presentation in the Smart Bulletin page of the SCMS, where the user can select a timeframe and a specific CEMT class to display the forecasted vessel navigability for.

4.4. Conformance to FENIX principles

The real-time operations management and decision support toolbox was architected in accordance with the federated interoperability principles established by the CEF FENIX project, ensuring seamless integration with European logistics data-sharing ecosystems. Central to its design is the adoption of the FENIX Broker technology, which enables decentralized service discovery, metadata management, and controlled access to digital resources across a network of heterogeneous platforms. The developed Broker component enables dynamic registration and querying of the toolbox services such as the ETA prediction, Track & Trace and the Smart Bulletin using a harmonized metadata schema and secure API interfaces. This architecture ensures scalable and decentralized connectivity among stakeholders, supporting real-time operational synchronisation across modes and corridors.

The classification of digital services adopted in FENIX guides the structuring of the toolbox's service interface. This classification system that is developed to ensure semantic alignment and discoverability across platforms outlines twelve core categories of services: track and trace/event handling, cargo monitoring, traffic management, parking services, slot management/reservation and booking, dangerous goods management, trip and capacity planning and matching, optimisation of customs services, gate management, emissions monitoring, catalogue services, and transport and cargo e-documentation. The SCMS toolbox adopts this taxonomy in the categories of:

- **track and trace/event handling** as the Track & Trace tool it enables real-time monitoring of inland vessels' geolocations along defined transport corridors, contributing to operational transparency and situational awareness
- **traffic management** as the Smart Bulletin tool provides predictive information on river water level enhancing decision-making for voyage planning, particularly on constrained or seasonal waterways where water level fluctuations significantly impact the feasibility and safety of inland navigation. This function is consistent with FENIX's broader interpretation of traffic management as encompassing not only vehicular or vessel movement but also the environmental and infrastructural conditions that affect navigability
- **trip and capacity planning and matching** as the ETA Calculation module that also incorporates average delays at river locks, supports tactical and strategic decision-making by enabling transport planners to predict arrival times more accurately, allocate capacity more efficiently, and optimise routing across modes and nodes. The use of lock delay data introduces dynamic and operational realism into the estimation process

Eventually, the toolbox modules developed in the context of the SCMS platform are discoverable and usable within a broader ecosystem of European logistics services so that cross-border collaboration and data-driven corridor management are fostered.

5. Software architecture elements

This chapter outlines the foundational components of the software architecture developed at D3.1 and how this translates to the implemented software that supports the SCMS platform. It provides a structured overview of the technologies employed, the architectural design principles guiding system development and key considerations related to security.

5.1. Technologies

The SCMS platform utilizes a more modern and well-integrated set of technologies designed to support high performance, feasibility, maintainability and scalability. Next, all specific tools and frameworks will be outlined that were included for the platform's architecture, backend, frontend, build pipeline and infrastructure components, as well as for necessary software testing procedures.

The technologies that were used to implement the **backend** part of the application are:

- **Laravel 10:** For a quicker application development, the Laravel 10 framework was selected, a robust and time-tested PHP web framework offering an expressive syntax and a wide range of integrated features [25].
- **Eloquent ORM:** Laravel's Eloquent is an object-relational mapper (ORM) that enables each database table to have a corresponding "Model" that is used to interact with that table, allowing developers to query and manage data in MySQL using syntax that is easy to understand [26].
- **Redis:** Serves a dual purpose within the system architecture as it functions as a caching layer to alleviate database load and enhance performance, while also acting as the backend for Laravel queues, enabling efficient and reliable asynchronous task execution [27].
- **Laravel Events:** An event-driven architecture is implemented through Laravel Events, enabling the use of components that are decoupled and real-time responsiveness through WebSocket protocol data broadcasting using Laravel Echo JavaScript library for the client part [28].
- **Laravel Queues:** They handle background job processing, using Redis to offload time consuming tasks like emailing or broadcasting events [29].
- **Laravel Logging:** Application logging is managed using Laravel's Monolog based logging system, supporting multiple channels and configurable log handling [30].
- **MySQL:** It serves as the primary relational database system, managed and handled by Laravel's ORM for structured and convenient data management [31].
- **phpMyAdmin:** Used for development purposes, it offers a web-based user-friendly interface for database viewing, query execution, and data administration [32].

Regarding the **frontend** part of the application, the following technologies were used:

- **Tailwind CSS:** It was selected for utility-first styling of HTML web elements, allowing for rapid interface design and consistent, maintainable styling conventions without the complexity of the declarative nature of CSS-style rules [33].
- **JavaScript and jQuery:** The platform uses JavaScript for more dynamic interactivity and incorporates the jQuery library for simplified Document Object Model (DOM) manipulation and asynchronous operations like AJAX calls to the backend [34].

- **Mapbox GL JS:** SCMS platform uses the Mapbox GL JS library to render high performance, interactive maps using vector tiles and WebGL for geospatial projection [35].
- **Google Maps JavaScript API:** Complementing Mapbox, it is used for location services, geocoding, and complementary map-based features [36].
- **Soketi:** A Pusher compatible WebSocket server, that works with Laravel Echo for frontend subscriptions to enable real time event streaming [37].

Additionally, for the **build and asset pipeline** integration the technologies that were put into service are:

- **Node.js:** It is a cross-platform JavaScript runtime environment required for executing JavaScript build tools, easing the transformation and bundling of frontend assets [38].
- **Vite:** A high-performance resource compilation build tool that allows for rapid development feedback and efficient production builds [39].
- **GitLab:** Used both as a Git repository for version control and as a CI/CD platform to automate testing, building, and deployment processes [47].

For the **infrastructure and deployment** tools, the following technologies were employed:

- **Docker:** Is used to containerize the SCMS platform, offering separate environments for testing development, and production deployment [40].
- **Laravel sail:** It provides a Docker environment that is configured and used only for local development by default, coming with built-in features like PHP, MySQL, Redis and other services that are required for having a complete development environment [41].
- **Nginx:** In production environment, it acts as the reverse proxy and web server, routing HTTP requests to the Laravel application and providing static assets [42].
- **Ubuntu 24.04 LTS:** The platform is hosted on Ubuntu 24.04, a long-term support Linux distribution providing stability and security [43].
- **Certbot:** Secure HTTPS connections are ensured using Certbot to issue and automatically renew SSL certificates from within a Docker container [44].

Finally, the **testing** process is succeeded using:

- **PHPUnit:** The most popular PHP testing framework is employed for backend logic unit testing, ensuring code integrity and dependability through automated testing [45].
- **Laravel Dusk:** A Laravel ecosystem library used for end-to-end browser testing, it mimics user behaviour and verifies front-end interactions in a controlled setting [46].

5.2. Architecture overview

The Synchro-modal Corridor Management System (SCMS) is built to support the real-time coordination of multimodal transport operations along inland waterways (IWW). Its architecture is designed with resilience in mind, helping the system stay functional even when unexpected disruptions like extreme weather or infrastructure failures occur. SCMS follows a layered approach that separates key functions: data is collected, processed, and stored independently from the application logic and user-facing components. This modular structure makes the system easier to maintain, scale, and adapt over time, especially as new technologies or operational needs emerge.

The architecture overview (Figure 13) reflects and extends the theoretical view described in chapter 4 of the Deliverable D3.1, supporting the real-time integration of sensor data (WP2), predictive analytics (WP5 Digital Twin), and decision-support services aimed at the users.

Figure 13 Corridor Management System Architecture

For the base of architecture, the **data sources & connectivity layer**, the SCMS system collects data from multiple varied sources including:

- External systems (e.g. EuRIS),
- Sensors and IoT gateways (WP2) like Smart Buoys
- The Digital Twin platform (WP5), which provides AI-based forecasts and predictive maintenance insights.

These data sources can provide information about navigability disruptions on the pilot rivers as discussed in Chapter 3.

The core of SCMS's business logic is the **middleware Layer**. It offers services for disruptions information processing, routing and re-routing decision support, severity estimation, alerting management and anomaly detection. Under the `app/` SCMS project directory, these services are supported by Laravel `Interfaces`, `Console/Commands`, `Events`, `Helpers`, `Middleware`, and `Services`, all working together to achieve optimal operational efficiency and produce valuable information for the SCMS users.

The **application layer** stands for the high-level business services that the user interface exposes to end users. These services are the:

- Early Detection & Info
- Disruption Impact Estimation
- Action Toolbox
- Corridor Observatory

In the SCMS code folder structure, each of these modules maps directly to specific controller classes located in `app/Http/Controllers` that handle the application layer services at a higher processing level than the previous layers. For example:

- `AlertController.php` for Early Detection & Info
- `RoutePlanningController.php` for Disruption Impact Estimation
- `ActionToolboxServicesController.php` for Action Toolbox
- `ObservatoryController.php` for Corridor Observatory

In the **configuration & data management** layer, a single relational database (MySQL) that is accessible via Laravel's Eloquent ORM contains all the historical and real-time data in the appropriate tables, while their processing happens in the middleware layer. Redis is also used to reduce latency in situations involving constant access by caching frequently asked database queries. Among the folder mappings are:

- `database/migrations/` for database schema version definitions,
- `app/Models/` for Eloquent entities.

The SCMS user interface (UI) is a combination of a traditional website that loads on demand from Controller actions and a Single Page Application (SPA) that combines the RESTful and WebSocket APIs that the backend offers. The frontend, which was constructed using Mapbox GL JS, JavaScript, jQuery, and Tailwind CSS, offers dynamic service dashboards and interactive geospatial visualizations. When necessary, server-side rendering is managed via Laravel's Blade templating engine, especially for fallback views. The user interface is located under:

- `resources/views/` for Blade templates,
- `resources/js/` for JavaScript and event bindings,
- `resources/css/` for CSS/Tailwind configurations.

To provide faster dynamic module reloading during development, the platform replaces the conventional Laravel Mix configuration with Vite, a JavaScript bundler and asset compiler for frontend build tooling.

5.3. Security remarks

In any modern web application, authentication is a fundamental requirement for ensuring that users can securely access personalized features, manage sensitive data, and interact with protected resources. Laravel 10 provides a robust and extensible authentication system that supports session-based and token-based mechanisms out of the box. In the SCMS platform, authentication is configured using Laravel's default `session`-based guard, as defined in the `auth.php` configuration file. The `web` guard is set as the default and uses the `session` driver to maintain user state across requests. This guard is linked to the `users` provider, which utilizes Laravel's Eloquent ORM to interact with the `App\Models\User` model, enabling tight integration with the database for user management.

Password reset functionality is also configured with a dedicated database table for password reset tokens includes expiration and throttling settings set both to 60 minutes to enhance security and prevent abuse of the services. Additionally, the password timeout is set to 10,800 seconds (3 hours), which determines how long a user can remain authenticated before being prompted to re-enter their password for sensitive operations.

The SCMS leverages Laravel's built-in Authorization and Policy features to authorize user actions against a given resource [48], in combination with the `spatie/laravel-permission` PHP package so that a strong and flexible authorization mechanism is implemented. This package simplifies the management of user roles and permissions by providing a structured interface for assigning and checking access rights across user models [49]. It integrates seamlessly with Laravel's gate and policy system, allowing for granular control over user actions. For development and debugging purposes, the `spatie/laravel-ignition` package is also utilized. It enhances the developer experience by offering detailed error pages, stack traces, and contextual insights during runtime, which are particularly useful when testing authorization flows and policy logic [50].

To ensure secure communication between third-party systems and the application's REST APIs that receive data from them, a custom middleware was implemented to authenticate external API clients. This middleware checks for a valid authorization token in the incoming request headers. That is issued independently for each interested API client. If a token is present, it verifies the token against a securely stored version in the database. When a match is found, the client is considered authenticated, and their identity is attached to the request for further processing. If the token is missing or invalid, the request is rejected with an appropriate unauthorized response. This approach gives the SCMS a lightweight and effective way to control access to its public-facing REST APIs, making sure that only trusted systems can interact with it. This topic will be covered in more detail in D3.5 where the integration of selected tools and data sources into the SCMS is examined.

6. Testing

Testing a modern web-application is essential to ensure quality, reliability and user satisfaction. Software testing is defined as “the process of verification and validation, checking whether it is meeting the users’ requirements” and plays “a vital role in the process of developing high quality software.” [1].

Additionally, testing is an essential tool for detecting flaws and assessing dependability during the phases of specification, design, and coding [2]. Web applications function in complex environments characterized by dynamic content, asynchronous operations and diverse browser and device interactions. These conditions necessitate robust testing strategies to ensure that functionality, security, performance, and usability are maintained in the code and user level.

The SCMS platform being itself a web application, was subject to rigorous testing activities. In this chapter three important layers of web application testing are outlined that were employed for testing the SCMS application: Unit Testing, API/HTTP Testing and Browser-Based User Acceptance Testing (UAT). The first two types of tests are handled using the PHPUnit framework, while Laravel Dusk was used for creating and running the Browser-Based UAT tests. PHPUnit provides an extensive set of assertions and test coverage tools, which makes it appropriate for verifying that the application logic functions as designed. Laravel Dusk, on the other hand, offers a simple, understandable API for simulating how people interact with the application in a real browser. When used in combination, these technologies aid in simplifying the testing procedure and lowering the complexity and effort related to testing web applications developed with PHP [3]. They also have excellent logical integration with the Laravel ecosystem, which allows for effective test cases development, better code maintainability, feasibility and automated browser testing that closely imitates actual user interactions.

6.1. Unit Testing

Unit Testing is a foundational software quality control technique that involves testing the smallest testable parts of an application, typically individual functions or methods to make sure they perform as expected in isolation [4]. It serves multiple important purposes in software development: validating code logic early, supporting refactoring, improving design through modularization, and offering assurance throughout the deployment cycles. To be more specific, Unit Testing provides fast, automated feedback throughout the development, which is particularly critical in environments where continuous integration and deployment (CI/CD) are practiced [5]. Furthermore, Unit Testing is particularly valuable in contemporary software development where applications are expected to be modular, scalable, and maintainable. By separating different code units, developers can find errors early before they reproduce into more complex layers of the system. This careful approach reduces debugging time and increases development efficiency. Also, in modern frameworks like Laravel, testing is closely integrated into the development workflow, allowing developers to write, run, and automate tests with minimal effort. When used systematically, unit testing encourages cleaner code architecture and supports long-term software evolution, especially in projects with multiple contributors or changing requirements.

In the SCMS application, unit tests were implemented to verify the functionality of various components. Tests for three key utility modules, `ValidationHelper.php`, `GeometryCalculationHelper.php`,

and `DataConversionHelper.php` are included as representative examples from the broader set of test cases.

ValidationHelper_Test.php

```
<?php

namespace Tests\Unit\Helpers;

use App\Helpers\ValidationHelper;
use Illuminate\Validation\ValidationException;
use Tests\TestCase;

class ValidationHelper_Test extends TestCase
{
    public function test_request_body_manual_validation_passes_valid_data()
    {
        $requestBody = ['name' => 'John B', 'email' => 'john@example.com'];
        $rules = ['name' => 'required|string', 'email' => 'required|email'];
        $result = ValidationHelper::requestBodyManualValidation($requestBody,
$rules);
        $this->assertEquals($requestBody, $result);
    }

    public function
test_request_body_manual_validation_throws_exception_on_invalid_data()
    {
        $requestBody = ['name' => '', 'email' => 'invalid-email'];
        $rules = ['name' => 'required|string', 'email' => 'required|email'];
        $this->expectException(ValidationException::class);
        ValidationHelper::requestBodyManualValidation($requestBody, $rules);
    }

    public function
test_request_body_manual_validation_handles_partial_valid_data()
    {
        $requestBody = ['name' => 'John B', 'email' => ''];
        $rules = ['name' => 'required|string', 'email' => 'required|email'];
        $this->expectException(ValidationException::class);
        ValidationHelper::requestBodyManualValidation($requestBody, $rules);
    }

    public function
test_format_validation_error_log_message_formats_correctly()
    {

```

```
        $errors = [  
            'name' => ['The name field is required.'],  
            'email' => ['The email must be a valid email address.'],  
        ];  
        $result = ValidationHelper::formatValidationErrorLogMessage($errors);  
        $expected = 'name => The name field is required., email => The email  
must be a valid email address.';  
        $this->assertEquals($expected, $result);  
    }  
  
    public function  
test_format_validation_error_log_message_handles_single_error()  
    {  
        $errors = ['name' => ['The name field is required.']];  
        $result = ValidationHelper::formatValidationErrorLogMessage($errors);  
        $expected = 'name => The name field is required.';  
        $this->assertEquals($expected, $result);  
    }  
  
    public function  
test_format_validation_error_log_message_handles_empty_array()  
    {  
        $errors = [];  
        $result = ValidationHelper::formatValidationErrorLogMessage($errors);  
        $this->assertEquals('', $result);  
    }  
}
```

The `ValidationHelper_Test.php` class verifies the accuracy and robustness of a custom validation use. The test `test_request_body_manual_validation_passes_valid_data()` supports that when valid data is provided (e.g., a correct name and email), the validation logic returns the data unchanged without raising objections.

On the other hand,

`test_request_body_manual_validation_throws_exception_on_invalid_data()` ensures that when the input fails to meet the defined rules, such as an empty name and incorrectly formatted email, a Validation Exception is thrown, thus applying proper data integrity.

A similar check is performed in,

`test_request_body_manual_validation_handles_partial_valid_data()`, where only one field is valid, ensuring the helper does not allow partial compliance. The next set of tests targets the logging phase of validation.

The `test_format_validation_error_log_message_formats_correctly()`, validates that multiple validation errors are formatted into a clear, comma-separated string, aiming in debugging and monitoring.

Finally, `test_format_validation_error_log_message_handles_single_error()` confirms the function works correctly even when only a single field error exists, while `test_format_validation_error_log_message_handles_empty_array()` ensures that no errors are formatted into an empty string, avoiding unintended messages in logs.

GeometryCalculationHelper_Test.php

```
<?php

namespace Tests\Unit;

use App\Helpers\GeometryCalculationHelper;
use Carbon\Carbon;
use PHPUnit\Framework\TestCase;

class GeometryCalculationHelper_Test extends TestCase
{
    public function testCalculateHaversineDistance()
    {
        $lat1 = 40.7128;
        $lon1 = -74.0060;
        $lat2 = 34.0522;
        $lon2 = -118.2437;

        $distance =
        GeometryCalculationHelper::calculateHaversineDistance($lat1, $lon1, $lat2,
        $lon2);

        $this->assertGreaterThan(3900000, $distance);
        $this->assertLessThan(4000000, $distance);
    }

    public function testCalculateVelocity()
    {
        $lat1 = 45.0;
        $lon1 = 9.0;
        $lat2 = 45.001;
        $lon2 = 9.001;

        $t1 = Carbon::now()->subMinutes(5)->toIso8601String();
```

```

    $t2 = Carbon::now()->toIso8601String();

    $velocity = GeometryCalculationHelper::calculateVelocity($lat1,
$lon1, $lat2, $lon2, $t2, $t1);

    $this->assertArrayHasKey('velocity', $velocity);
    $this->assertGreaterThan(0, $velocity['velocity']);
  }

  public function testDecodeGoogleMapsPolyline()
  {
    // Simple encoded polyline with two points
    $encoded = '_p~iF~ps|U_u1LnnqC_mqNvxq`@';
    $points =
GeometryCalculationHelper::decodeGoogleMapsPolyline($encoded);

    $this->assertIsArray($points);
    $this->assertCount(3, $points);
    $this->assertEquals([38.5, -120.2], $points[0]);
  }

  public function testConvertGoogleDirectionsResponseToGeojson()
  {
    $mockResponse = [
      'routes' => [
        [
          'overview_polyline' => ['points' =>
'_p~iF~ps|U_u1LnnqC_mqNvxq`@'],
          'summary' => 'Test Route',
          'legs' => [
            [
              'distance' => ['text' => '10 km', 'value' =>
10000],
              'duration' => ['text' => '15 mins', 'value' =>
900],
              'start_address' => 'Start',
              'end_address' => 'End'
            ]
          ]
        ]
      ]
    ];
  }

```

```
        $geojson =
GeometryCalculationHelper::convertGoogleDirectionsResponseToGeojson($mockResponse);

        $this->assertEquals('Feature', $geojson['type']);
        $this->assertEquals('LineString', $geojson['geometry']['type']);
        $this->assertCount(3, $geojson['geometry']['coordinates']);
    }
}
```

The `GeometryCalculationHelper_Test.php` class focuses on geographical and geometric utility methods used to process map and distance data. The `testCalculateHaversineDistance()` function tests the implementation of the Haversine formula, confirming that the calculated distance between two major cities, falls within an expected and realistic place.

The `testCalculateVelocity()` test evaluates the result of the method that calculates speed based on geospatial coordinates and timestamps. It declares that the method returns an array containing a non-zero velocity that ensures practical applicability for use cases like tracing movement.

The `testDecodeGoogleMapsPolyline()` tests whether encoded polylines (used in mapping APIs like Google Maps) are correctly decoded into a sequence of latitude and longitude coordinates.

Lastly, the `testConvertGoogleDirectionsResponseToGeojson()` test validates the alteration of a mock Google Directions API response into a properly structured GeoJSON format. It checks that the output contains the correct geometry type (LineString) and expected number of coordinates, making the data a good fit for geospatial applications such as web map rendering.

DataConversionHelper_Test.php

```
<?php

namespace Tests\Unit\Helpers;

use App\Helpers\DataConversionHelper;
use Tests\TestCase;

class DataConversionHelper_Test extends TestCase
{
    public function
test_arabic_number_to_roman_converts_correctly_for_seven()
    {
        $result = DataConversionHelper::arabicNumberToRoman(7);
        $this->assertEquals('VII', $result);
    }
}
```

```
public function
test_arabic_number_to_roman_converts_correctly_for_three()
{
    $result = DataConversionHelper::arabicNumberToRoman(3);
    $this->assertEquals('III', $result);
}

public function test_arabic_number_to_roman_handles_zero()
{
    $result = DataConversionHelper::arabicNumberToRoman(0);
    $this->assertEquals('', $result);
}

public function test_arabic_number_to_roman_handles_one()
{
    $result = DataConversionHelper::arabicNumberToRoman(1);
    $this->assertEquals('I', $result);
}

public function test_roman_to_arabic_number_converts_correctly_for_vi()
{
    $result = DataConversionHelper::romanToArabicNumber('VI');
    $this->assertEquals(6, $result);
}

public function test_roman_to_arabic_number_converts_correctly_for_ix()
{
    $result = DataConversionHelper::romanToArabicNumber('IX');
    $this->assertEquals(9, $result);
}

public function test_roman_to_arabic_number_handles_invalid_input()
{
    $result = DataConversionHelper::romanToArabicNumber('Z');
    $this->assertEquals(0, $result);
}

public function test_roman_to_arabic_number_handles_case_insensitivity()
{
    $result = DataConversionHelper::romanToArabicNumber('vi');
    $this->assertEquals(6, $result);
}
}
```

The `DataConversionHelper_Test.php` class verifies two-way conversions between Arabic and Roman numerals. The test `test_arabic_number_to_roman_converts_correctly_for_seven()` checks that the helper correctly converts the number 7 to 'VII', while `test_arabic_number_to_roman_converts_correctly_for_three()` verifies a similar alliteration for the number 3. The `test_arabic_number_to_roman_handles_zero()` secures that the function gracefully handles zero, an edge case not representable in Roman numerals—by returning an empty string. Another section that was tested was the `test_arabic_number_to_roman_handles_one()`, that confirms that the number “1” is correctly converted to the roman character “I”.

In the meantime, the reverse operation is tested in `test_roman_to_arabic_number_converts_correctly_for_vi()` and `test_roman_to_arabic_number_converts_correctly_for_ix()`, which validate the conversion of 'VI' and 'IX' to the numbers “6” and “9” respectively. Edge cases are also considered: `test_roman_to_arabic_number_handles_invalid_input()` checks that an invalid Roman string such as 'Z' returns 0 rather than causing errors, and `test_roman_to_arabic_number_handles_case_insensitivity()` ensures the conversion works regardless of input case by testing the lowercase 'vi'.

6.2. API/HTTP Testing

API/HTTP Testing is an essential component of guaranteeing the authenticity and reliability of web applications. It involves sending simulated requests to endpoints and verifying the correctness of responses, including payload structures, status codes, and error handling. This layer of testing focuses on how different components communicate over HTTP, especially between client and server, and is vital for maintaining consistent and secure integrations in microservice and RESTful architectures [6].

Unlike unit tests that assess internal logic, API tests evaluate the external behaviour of an application from the perspective of consumers, testing not only expected success cases but also input validation and security constraints such as authentication and authorization [7]. Because APIs often function as the backbone of frontend-backend communication, defects at this level can significantly impair application usability. Therefore, early and continuous API testing enables faster detection of logic flaws and contributes to higher system reliability, particularly when integrated into CI/CD workflows [8].

Laravel provides a robust feature testing framework that makes it easy to affect real HTTP requests and assert conditions on the returned responses. In the SCMS application, API testing was managed using Laravel's built-in HTTP testing capabilities based on PHPUnit against the `/api/aipo/ntcs` endpoint used for receiving NtS information about the Po River of the Italian Pilot. The test class verifies the API's ability to correctly handle authenticated inquiries, confirm input structures and respond appropriately to inaccurate or deformed data.

AIPoNtCsTest.php

```
<?php

namespace Tests\Feature;

use Illuminate\Testing\Fluent\AssertableJson;
use Tests\TestCase;

class AIPoNtCsTest extends TestCase
{
    /**
     * The requests' base url.
     *
     * @var string
     */
    protected $baseUrl;

    /**
     * The requests' initial payload.
     *
     * @var array
     */
    protected $payload;

    /**
     * The API client key.
     * Replace it with a valid one to test the successful response test.
     *
     * @var string
     */
    protected $apiKey;

    /**
     * Set up the testing suite before running the actual tests, like
    defining
     * variables, creating users, seeding data, setting up headers etc.
     *
     * @return void
     */
    protected function setUp(): void
    {
        parent::setUp();
    }
}
```

```

    $this->baseUrl = '/api/aipo/ntcs';
    $this->apiKey = 'an_invalid_API_key'; // By default an invalid API
key
    $this->payload = [
        "items" => [
            [
                "organisation" => "AIPO",
                "countryCode" => "CZ",
                "country" => "Czech Republic",
                "dateIssue" => "2024-09-06T10:20:22+02:00",
                "dateStart" => "2024-09-06T00:00:00+02:00",
                "dateEnd" => "2024-09-06T00:00:00+02:00",
                "messageType" => 4,
                "messageTypeMessage" => "weather message",
                "title" => "weather message Dolni Vltava, from km 26.5 to
km 27.5",

                "number" => "2024/1615/0",
                "noticeText" => "example notice text",
                "limitations" => [
                    "NOSERV",
                    "OBSTRU"
                ],
                "geometry" => [
                    "x" => 4.79849,
                    "y" => 46.157300000000006
                ]
            ]
        ]
    ];
}

/**
 * Test the NtCs were successfully created.
 */
public function test_ntcs_successfully_created(): void
{
    $response = $this->withHeaders([
        'Authorization' => "Bearer {$this->apiKey}",
    ])->post($this->baseUrl, $this->payload);

    $response
        ->assertStatus(201)
        ->assertJson(fn (AssertableJson $json) =>

```

```
        $json->where('message', 'AIPO Notices to Skippers processed
successfully.')
        ->hasAll(['status', 'processed_items'])
    );
}

/**
 * Test there are validation errors.
 */
public function test_ntcs_throw_validation_errors(): void
{
    // Items is empty
    $payload = $this->payload;
    $payload['items'] = '';
    $response = $this->withHeaders([
        'Authorization' => "Bearer {$this->apiKey}",
    ])->post($this->baseUrl, $payload);

    $response
        ->assertStatus(422)
        ->assertJson(fn (AssertableView $json) =>
            $json->where('status', 422)
                ->where('message', 'Validation errors in request.')
                ->has('validation_errors')
                ->has('validation_errors.items', fn (AssertableView
$json) =>
                    $json->where(0, 'The items field is required.')
                    ->etc()
                )
            );

    // Organisation is too short
    $payload = $this->payload;
    $payload['items'][0]['organisation'] = 'G';
    $response = $this->withHeaders([
        'Authorization' => "Bearer {$this->apiKey}",
    ])->post($this->baseUrl, $payload);

    $response
        ->assertStatus(422)
        ->assertJson(fn (AssertableView $json) =>
            $json->where('status', 422)
                ->where('message', 'Validation errors in request.')
```

```

        ->has('validation_errors', fn (AssertableView $json) =>
            $json
                ->where('items.0.organisation', [
                    'The items.0.organisation field must be at
least 2 characters.',
                ])
                ->etc()
        )
    );

    // Longitude is not a numerical value
    $payload = $this->payload;
    $payload['items'][0]['geometry']['x'] = 'abcde';
    $response = $this->withHeaders([
        'Authorization' => "Bearer {$this->apiKey}",
    ])->post($this->baseUrl, $payload);

    $response
        ->assertStatus(422)
        ->assertJson(fn (AssertableView $json) =>
            $json->where('status', 422)
                ->where('message', 'Validation errors in request.')
                ->has('validation_errors', fn (AssertableView $json) =>
                    $json
                        ->where('items.0.geometry.x', [
                            'The items.0.geometry.x field must be a
number.',
                        ])
                        ->etc()
                )
        );
}

/**
 * Test the API client calling this API is not authenticated.
 */
public function test_api_client_not_authenticated(): void
{
    $apiKey = 'an_invalid_api_key';
    $response = $this->withHeaders([
        'Authorization' => "Bearer {$apiKey}",
    ])->post($this->baseUrl, $this->payload);
}

```

```
$response
    ->assertStatus(401)
    ->assertJson(fn (AsserttableJson $json) =>
        $json->where('message', 'Unauthorized')
    );
}
```

The `AIPoNtCsTest.php` class focuses on affecting real-world HTTP interactions with the AIPo Notices to Skippers endpoint. A base URL (`/api/aipo/ntcs`) and a predefined payload are configured in the `setUp()` method to regulate inputs across test cases. The tests are executed with different headers, data configurations, and expected results to cover the API's most critical pathways.

The `test_ntcs_successfully_created()` test checks the success path of the API. When valid data and a reasonable authentication header are passed, the API should respond with HTTP status 201 Created and return a JSON body holding a success message (AIPo Notices to Skippers processed successfully.), a status field, and an array of `processed_items`. The response structure is declared using Laravel's `AsserttableJson`, ensuring that the correct data fields are included and well-formed. This fact ensures that the endpoint processes data correctly under typical conditions. Equally important is the `test_ntcs_throw_validation_errors()`, as this method tests the API's input validation by mimicking three error cases:

- The first test sends an empty `items` field and expects a 422 response with a `validation_errors.items` message.
- The second test provides an invalid `organization` field that is too short, triggering a field-specific validation message.
- The third test assigns a non-numeric string to the `geometry.x` (longitude) field, resulting in a numeric validation error.

Last, is the `test_api_client_not_authenticated()` test which submits the correct payload but with an invalid API key. The server is expected to return a 401 Unauthorized status along with an appropriate message (Unauthorized). This confirms the API's ability to reject unauthorized requests and protect access to sensitive functionality, a critical part of any secure API implementation.

6.3. Browser/User Acceptance Testing

Browser or User Acceptance Testing (UAT) verifies that a system behaves correctly from the perspective of the end user. This form of testing focuses on validating complete user flows, interface behavior, client-side validation, and visual consistency across the web application. Unlike unit or API tests that assess isolated logic or endpoint responses, browser tests confirm that all layers of the application integrate and render correctly in a real browser environment [9]. UAT plays a crucial role in ensuring that business requirements are fulfilled and that the application provides seamless user experience prior to software release [10].

Laravel Dusk was used to implement browser tests for the SCMS platform. Dusk allows for automation of browser interactions using clean, fluent syntax, making it suitable for simulating realistic user actions such as clicking buttons, filling out forms, waiting for dynamic content and validating database states. This library makes sure that the front-end components perform as intended across different scenarios and devices, offering confidence that core functionalities remain stable during iterative development [11].

Among others, three browser test classes will be presented to verify key user journeys:

`EarlyDetectionTest.php`, `RegisterTest.php`, and `VesselManagementTest.php`.

EarlyDetectionTest.php

```
<?php

namespace Tests\Browser;

use Laravel\Dusk\Browser;
use Tests\DuskTestCase;
use App\Models\River;

class EarlyDetectionTest extends DuskTestCase
{
    public function testEarlyDetectionPage()
    {
        $this->browse(function (Browser $browser) {
            $river = River::where('name', 'Po')->first();

            $browser->visit('/service')
                ->assertPresent('button.alerts_river[data-id="' . $river->id . '"']')
                ->click('button.alerts_river[data-id="' . $river->id . '"']')
                ->assertSeeIn('.alerts_river.bg-blue-700', 'PO')
                ->radio('sender', 'all_senders')
                ->assertRadioSelected('sender', 'all_senders')
                ->type('.alert_from', '01/06/2024')
                ->type('.alert_to', '30/06/2024')
                ->assertInputValue('.alert_from', '01/06/2024')
                ->assertInputValue('.alert_to', '30/06/2024')
                ->click('#find_alerts')
                ->waitFor('#alerts_grid_container:not(:empty)', 10);

            $this->assertDatabaseHas('alerts', [
                'river_id' => $river->id,
                'valid_from' => '2024-06-14 00:00:00',
            ]);
        });
    }
}
```

```
    });  
  }  
}
```

This test validates the functionality of the Early Detection & Info page by interacting with the `/service` page. It assumes the selection of a specific river (Po) and applies date filters via UI form controls. After submitting the alert filter request, the test checks that the alerts grid is populated and that similar backend records exist. Assertions are used to confirm the presence of expected DOM elements (`.alerts_river.bg-blue-700`) and proper user input retention in date fields. The test ensures that the alert system behaves correctly in a user-driven workflow, confirming both UI responsiveness and data integrity.

RegisterTest.php

```
<?php  
  
namespace Tests\Browser;  
  
use Laravel\Dusk\Browser;  
use Tests\DuskTestCase;  
  
class RegisterTest extends DuskTestCase  
{  
    use \Illuminate\Foundation\Testing\WithFaker;  
  
    /**  
     * Test successful registration without a company.  
     */  
    public function test_user_can_register_without_company()  
    {  
        $this->browse(function (Browser $browser) {  
            $firstName = $this->faker->firstName;  
            $lastName = $this->faker->lastName;  
            $email = $this->faker->unique()->safeEmail;  
            $password = 'a_strong_password';  
  
            $browser->visit('/register')  
                ->assertSee('Create an Account')  
                ->assertSee('Please fill in your details below')  
                ->type('#first_name', $firstName)  
                ->type('#last_name', $lastName)  
                ->type('#email', $email)  
                ->type('#password', $password)  
                ->type('#password_confirmation', $password)  
                ->check('#accept_terms')  
        });  
    }  
}
```

```

        ->assertNotChecked('#company_checkbox')
        ->press('Register');

$this->assertDatabaseHas('users', [
    'fname' => $firstName,
    'lname' => $lastName,
    'email' => $email,
    'email_verified_at' => null,
]);

$this->assertDatabaseMissing('companies', [
    'name' => null,
]);

$user = \App\Models\User::where('email', $email)->first();
$this->assertTrue($user-
>hasRole(\App\Enums\RolesEnum::Stakeholder->value));
    });
}

/**
 * Test successful registration with a company.
 */
public function test_user_can_register_with_company()
{
    $this->browse(function (Browser $browser) {
        $firstName = $this->faker->firstName;
        $lastName = $this->faker->lastName;
        $email = $this->faker->unique()->safeEmail;
        $password = ' a_strong_password';
        $companyName = $this->faker->company;

        $browser->visit('/register')
            ->assertSee('Create an Account')
            ->type('#first_name', $firstName)
            ->type('#last_name', $lastName)
            ->type('#email', $email)
            ->type('#password', $password)
            ->type('#password_confirmation', $password)
            ->check('#company_checkbox')
            ->waitFor('#boating_company_container', 5)
            ->type('#company_name', $companyName)
            ->check('#accept_terms')
    });
}

```

```
        ->press('Register')
        ->screenshot('register_with_company');

$this->assertDatabaseHas('users', [
    'fname' => $firstName,
    'lname' => $lastName,
    'email' => $email,
    'email_verified_at' => null,
]);

$this->assertDatabaseHas('companies', [
    'name' => $companyName,
    'type' => 'Boating Company',
]);

$user = \App\Models\User::where('email', $email)->first();
$this->assertTrue($user-
>hasRole(\App\Enums\RolesEnum::CompanyAdmin->value));
    });
}

/**
 * Test password visibility toggle functionality.
 */
public function test_password_visibility_toggle()
{
    $this->browse(function (Browser $browser) {
        $password = 'a_strong_password';

        $browser->visit('/register')
            ->type('#password', $password)
            ->assertInputValue('#password', $password)
            ->assertAttribute('#password', 'type', 'password')
            ->click('#togglePassword')
            ->waitFor('#iconHide:not(.hidden)', 5)
            ->assertAttribute('#password', 'type', 'text')
            ->click('#togglePassword')
            ->waitFor('#iconShow:not(.hidden)', 5)
            ->assertAttribute('#password', 'type', 'password');

    });
}
}
```

The `RegisterTest.php` class evaluates the end-to-end registration process under multiple conditions. The first one is the `test_user_can_register_without_company()` simulates a basic registration without company affiliation. The test verifies that the user is added to the database and that no company is created. It also confirms role assignment (Stakeholder) based on application logic. The second test is the `test_user_can_register_with_company()`, the optional company registration path. Upon checking the company registration box, the UI reveals additional fields. The test simulates entering the required information and verifies that both the user and the company records persisted. Role assignment is also validated to ensure the user is designated as a `CompanyAdmin`. The third and last test is the `test_password_visibility_toggle()`, which verifies the functionality of a password visibility toggle. It confirms that toggling between visible and hidden password states updates the input type and icon visibility correctly. In conclusion, these tests confirm that the registration form responds dynamically, enforces expected behaviour, and handles both data and UI state transitions accurately [12].

VesselManagementTest.php

```
<?php

namespace Tests\Browser;

use Laravel\Dusk\Browser;
use Tests\DuskTestCase;
use App\Models\Company;
use App\Models\User;
use App\Models\River;

class VesselManagementTest extends DuskTestCase
{
    public function test_user_can_create_vessel()
    {
        $this->browse(function (Browser $browser) {
            $companyId = Company::factory()->create()->id;
            $user = User::factory()->withCompanyAdminRole()->create([
                'company_id' => $companyId,
            ]);

            $river = River::where('name', 'Po')->first();

            $uuid = fake()->uuid();
            $browser->loginAs($user)
                ->visit("/companies/{$companyId}?active_tab=vessels")
                ->assertSee('My Vessels')
                ->click('#add_vessel')
                ->assertSee('Add Vessel')
                ->type('name', "Test Vessel {$uuid}")
                ->type('register', fake()->bothify('REG###??'))
        });
    }
}
```

```
->type('imo', fake()->bothify('IMO#####'))
->select('river_id', $river->id)
->select('boat_class_id', 3)
->type('own_capacity', 100)
->type('own_length', 20)
->type('own_beam', 5)
->type('own_speed', 15)
->type('own_draught', 2)
->type('own_height', 10)
->type('own_tonnage', 50)
->select('capacity_unit', 'TEU')
->press('Save')
->assertPathIs("/companies/{companyId}")
->assertQueryStringHas('active_tab', 'vessels')
->assertSee("Test Vessel {$uuid}");

$this->assertDatabaseHas('boats', [
    'name' => "Test Vessel {$uuid}",
    'river_id' => $river->id,
]);
});
}
}
```

This test tries to simulate a user with the CompanyAdmin role managing vessel records from the company dashboard. It navigates to the `/companies/{id}?active_tab=vessels` page, interacts with the “Add Vessel” modal, and completes comprehensive vessel details. After submission, it verifies that the vessel appears in the UI and that the same data is stored in the database. The test ensures that users can create new Vessel entities using complicated forms and that the full interaction from login to entity creation works without error. By checking front-end rendering and backend persistence, the test confirms one of the most complex and business-critical flows in the system [13].

7. SCMS services access tutorial

The SCMS is a central digital infrastructure developed within T3.3 of the CRISTAL project, designed to support intelligent, resilient, and cooperative IWW transport and logistics operations. This chapter is dedicated to guiding users through the process of registering on the platform and gaining full access to its services. For a more hands-on experience, a series of short, detailed video tutorials covering the main functionalities of the system is available directly on the online platform, allowing users to quickly learn and navigate the features with ease.

7.1. User personas

The SCMS platform is designed to serve a diverse ecosystem of users involved in IWT, logistics coordination, infrastructure management, and climate resilience planning. To ensure usability and relevance across all operational and strategic levels, the following key user personas have been identified. These personas reflect both the technical roles defined within the platform and the real-world actors engaged in the CRISTAL project.

1. System Administrators

- *Platform Role:* System Admin
- *Typical Users:* IT leads from the responsible consortium partner, CERTH

2. Company Administrators

- *Platform Role:* Company Admin
- *Typical Users:* Logistics managers, fleet coordinators, operations directors from shipping companies, barge operators

3. Company Operators

- *Platform Role:* Company Ops
- *Typical Users:* Dispatchers, control room staff, transport planners, field operators, skippers/vessel captains and crew

4. Stakeholders

- *Platform Role:* Stakeholder
- *Typical Users:* Public authorities, infrastructure managers, environmental agencies, research institutions, pilot site coordinators, project partners

Understanding these personas helps tailor the SCMS interface, workflows and training materials to the specific needs of each user group. It also ensures that the system supports both operational efficiency and strategic resilience, aligning with the goals of T3.3, from early detection and climate adaptation to dynamic planning and real-time decision support. Identifying the user personas is the stepping stone upon which the use case analysis will be built.

7.2. Use cases

The following table outlines the user personas, their platform roles, primary use cases and relevant SCMS services.

Table 3 User personas and use case mapping

User Persona	Platform Role	Primary Use Cases	Relevant SCMS Services
System Administrator	System Admin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Configure and maintain the SCMS platform - Manage global system settings, integrations, and security - Oversee user access and permissions across organizations - Ensure system uptime and data integrity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Admin panel (overall system management) • Early Detection & Info (data availability) • Disruption Impact Estimation (data pipelines) • Action Toolbox Services (service orchestration) • Corridor Observatory (data pipelines) • Quick Tutorial (update frequently with new info)
Company Administrator	Company Admin	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Register and manage company-specific assets (vessels) - Onboard and manage internal users - Set operational preferences for alerts email notifications - Monitor corridor-level KPIs 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My Company (company + assets administration) • Early Detection & Info (alerts) • Disruption Impact Estimation (navigability) • Action Toolbox Services (response coordination) • Corridor Observatory (metrics, KPIs monitoring) • Quick Tutorial (platform usage info)
Company Operator	Company Ops	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Execute daily planning and monitoring tasks - Respond to real-time alerts and disruptions - Use dynamic routing tools - Coordinate with other operators and stakeholders - Support emergency response and maintenance feedback loops - Receive real-time 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My Company (company + assets overview, own vessel route planning) • Early Detection & Info (weather, infrastructure, climate alerts) • Disruption Impact Estimation (routing impact, ETA changes) • Action Toolbox Services (track & trace, routing planning)

		navigability alerts and route updates - Report on-the-ground conditions and anomalies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Quick Tutorial (platform usage info)
Stakeholder	Stakeholder	- Access strategic data insights and climate indicators - Participate in corridor-level planning and policy discussions - Monitor infrastructure conditions and long-term climate projections - Facilitate SCMS deployment and testing at pilot sites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • My Account (alerts preferences) • Early Detection & Info (climate projections, infrastructure condition) • Disruption Impact Estimation (long-term planning scenarios) • Action Toolbox Services (resilience planning tools) • Corridor Observatory (metrics, KPIs monitoring) • Quick Tutorial (platform usage info)

The user personas and their associated use cases for the appropriate SCMS services outlined in the table above are pivotal to the successful implementation and operational efficacy of the SCMS within the CRISTAL project. Having made a clear definition of the above, it is ensured that all the developed SCMS services serve well all kinds of stakeholders and users, while being aligned with the CRISTAL project requirements.

7.3. Company, Regular User and Administration pages usage

In modern business applications, logical management of organizational data is critical for operational success. The My Company, My Account and Admin Panel pages of this application provide strong tools for company administrators, regular users and system administrators to inspect company details, user accounts, and vessel information. These interfaces authorize users to configure notification preferences, update company profiles, manage passwords, and handle vessel and user data with clarity. This section will analyse comprehensive guide tutorials on how to navigate and utilize these pages.

The My Company page was designed to streamline the management of company related data. It presents a responsive, user-friendly interface with a gradient titled Account Details, a sidebar navigation with three tabs (User Details, Vessels, and Users) and a main content area that is dynamically updated according to the selected tab (Figure 14). In order to access this page, users must login to their accounts and use the application's main menu navigation bar to reach the Company Page.

Figure 14 My Company Page, User Details – Email Notifications off

On to the first tab of the sidebar menu, the company users can view the User Details page which is also the default view when they enter the Company page. This page offers tools to configure if they want to receive email notifications and update company information and change account passwords. More specifically, the users can enable and disable email notifications by clicking on the toggling checkboxes under the “Do you want to receive email Notifications?” text. Likewise, the options under “Alerts on river accidents” text allow the user to select what rivers they wish to get an update alerts email for (Figure 15).

Figure 15 My Company Page, User Details – Email Notifications on

Notices to Skippers from EuRIS

Seine

Number: 2024/8625/33 (Voies navigables de France)
Title: delay - Seine a l'amont de Paris, No7 Du Coudray (Morsang-sur-Seine)
Limitations: delay
Country: France
Related Fairways: Seine
Organization: Voies navigables de France
Issue Date: 2024-11-05T08:37:40
Start Date: 2024-11-05T00:00:00
End Date: 2025-08-15T00:00:00

Moselle

Number: 2025/2257/0 (Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes)
Title: blockage - Zeltingen
Limitations: blockage
Country: France
Related Fairways: Moselle
Organization: Wasserstraßen- und Schifffahrtsverwaltung des Bundes
Issue Date: 2025-08-07T14:28:48
Start Date: 2025-08-08T00:00:00
End Date: 2025-08-08T00:00:00

Kind Regards
 Synchromodal Corridor Management System

Figure 16 Email Notification for alerts on Seine and Moselle rivers

Moreover, this page includes the “My Company” section which contains fields with company information that the users can edit, like the company details (name, registration, type, email, web address, address, country, postal code and city). These fields are presented in a two-column grid to ease the readability of the information (Figure 17).

Account Details

User_Details

Vessels

Users

Do you want to receive email Notifications ?

e-mail

Alerts on river accidents

Po Seine Moselle Vistula

My Company

Name	<input type="text" value="CERTH IWW Shipping Services"/>	Registration	<input type="text"/>
Type	<input type="text" value="Boating Company"/>		
Email	<input type="text" value="example@email.gr"/>	Web Address	<input type="text" value="https://www.example.gr/"/>
Address	<input type="text"/>	Country	<input type="text" value="Greece"/>
Postal Code	<input type="text"/>	City	<input type="text"/>

Figure 17 My Company details panel

Additionally, the User Details page has a “Change Password” functionality to update the account password by entering a new password (minimum 8 characters) and confirming the old password. This provides users with a secure way of changing the accounts’ passwords. Once preferences have been adjusted properly, clicking on the “Save Changes” button the changes are saved and a success confirmation message in the form of a popup toast panel with the text “Company information updated” is shown (Figure 18).

Account Details

User_Details
Vessels
Users

Company information updated

Do you want to receive email Notifications ?
 e-mail

Alerts on river accidents
 Po Seine Moselle Vistula

My Company

Name	<input type="text" value="CERTH IWW Shipping Services"/>	Registration	<input type="text"/>
Type	<input type="text" value="Boating Company"/>		
Email	<input type="text"/>	Web Address	<input type="text"/>
Address	<input type="text"/>	Country	<input type="text" value="Greece"/>
Postal Code	<input type="text"/>	City	<input type="text"/>

Change Password

New Password	Old Password
<input type="password" value="*****"/>	<input type="password" value="*****"/>
<small>* Password must be at least 8 characters.</small>	<small>* Please confirm your old password.</small>

Save Changes

Figure 18 Successful editing of My Company information

On the second tab of the sidebar menu, the stakeholders can view the Vessels page. The Vessels page displays a table listing all the company's vessels with their name, the associated river and it also provides to the users the options of viewing, adding, editing or deleting a vessel, while the arrow button redirects the users to a dedicated "Route planning page" for the specified vessel (Figure 19). In case there are not any vessels registered, a "No Records" message appears (Figure 20).

Figure 19 My Vessels panel with existing vessels

Figure 20 My Vessels panel without existing vessels

When clicking the “+ Add Vessel” button a modal dialog is displayed with fields for filling out vessel information like Name, Registration, IMO number, River, Vessel Class and Capacity (Figure 21). If the Vessel is saved after clicking the “Save” button, a toast notification is displayed on the bottom right of the page, confirming the success of the action or even highlighting a possible failure of the action e.g. due to input data validation errors (Figure 22).

Figure 21 Add Vessel modal dialog

Figure 22 My Vessels panel with vessel creation success message

The “View” icon (eye) opens a modal dialog that displays the vessel details e.g., name, registration, IMO, river, class and capacity in a read-only format (Figure 23).

Figure 23 View Vessel modal dialog

The “Edit” icon (pencil) opens a modal dialog with editable fields of the vessel that are already filled out with the vessel's information when it was originally created. The users can modify the existing vessel's details and save them (Figure 24).

Figure 24 Edit Vessel modal dialog

The “Delete” icon (trash bin) enables the deletion of a specific vessel, asking for a confirmation of the action from the user (Figure 25).

Figure 25 Delete Vessel modal dialog

The “Route Planning” icon (redirect arrow) navigates the user to a dedicated page for vessel route planning. As mentioned in section 4.3, the system’s Route Planning Assessment function enables intelligent IWW route planning by considering user inputs such as departure time, vessel speed and vessel characteristics. It provides ETA, CO₂ emissions, disruption specifics, multimodal alternatives, and geospatial data, and evaluates feasibility based on infrastructure limits, real-time navigability alerts, and predicted interruptions from the Digital Twin (Figure 26).

Figure 26 Route assessment for a specific company vessel

Finally, in the third tab of the sidebar menu of My Company page, the company users can access the Users page. This page displays a table listing of the Company’s users’ first name, last name, role, email, and they have options to add a new SCMS user associated to their Company. As company administrators, they can also view, edit and delete other company users of the same company (Figure 27 and Figure 28).

Figure 27 My Company page, Users panel

Figure 28 My Company page, Users panel – View User modal dialog

The My Account user page is a user-centric interface designed to enable the management of personal information and notification settings for Stakeholder users, like the My Company one. It features a clean, responsive layout with a header titled “Account Details,” a sidebar navigation with a single User Details tab and a main content area for data interaction. The page uses a toast notification system for real-time feedback and includes form fields for updating personal details and passwords. In particular, the Regular User page excludes the Vessels and Users tabs because these functionalities are reserved for the Company members-related roles. To access the My Account page, users log in with their credentials and navigate through the application’s main menu or dashboard (Figure 29).

Figure 29 My Account page

The Admin Panel page is a tool designed to assist system-wide management. It features a responsive layout with a gradient header, a main content area divided into three sections (System Administrators, Companies, and Stakeholders) and a toast notification system for page actions feedback. The Companies section displays detailed information about each company, including its vessels and users. The page includes modals for confirming deletions and buttons for adding new records, with permission-based access controls ensuring secure operations. To access the Admin Panel page, users with system administrator rights log in and navigate via the application’s main menu or dashboard (Figure 30).

The System Administrators section allows system administrators to view, edit, delete, and add admin accounts, securing proper inspection of high-level access.

The first section of the page displays a table list with all the system administrators, showing their Username (email), First and Last name. If no administrators exist, a “No records. Please add an Admin” message is displayed with a red border (Figure 31).

Figure 30 Admin panel page, System Administrators section

Figure 31 Admin panel page, System Administrators section – No records

To add a new system administrator, the users can click on the “+ Add an Admin” button, which redirects to a system administrator creation page. The creation page of a new admin requires the user to fill out the fields of Personal Details (First Name, Last Name and Email Address) and Account Security (Password and Confirm Password) and then click the “+ Create User” button (Figure 32).

Figure 32 Add new system administrator page

After, the user has been created and exists, the user can edit, view and delete the created system administrator. By clicking the “Show details” button, one can see the profile information of a specific admin (Figure 33).

The screenshot shows a user profile page titled "Profile Information". At the top, there is a blue header with the title. Below the header, the user's name "Example Test" and role "System Admin" are displayed next to a circular profile picture containing the letter "E". Underneath, a section titled "User Information" contains two columns of details. The left column, "Basic Information", lists "Full Name: Example Test" and "Role: System Admin". The right column, "Contact Details", lists "Email: example@gmail.com" and "Registered: 13 minutes ago". At the bottom center, there is a "Close" button with an "X" icon.

Figure 33 View system administrator page

By clicking the “Edit” button next to an administrator the user is redirected to an edit page, which allows them to update the admin details and save them to the system (Figure 34).

The screenshot shows an "Edit User Profile" page. It features a blue header with the title. The user's name "Example Test" and role "System Admin" are shown at the top. Below, the "User Information" section is divided into two columns. The left column, "Personal Details", has input fields for "First Name" (containing "Example") and "Last Name" (containing "Test"). The right column, "Contact Details", has an input field for "Email Address" (containing "example@gmail.com"). At the bottom, there are two buttons: a blue "Save Changes" button with a checkmark icon and a white "Cancel" button with an "X" icon.

Figure 34 Edit system administrator page

Yet, to delete an admin, the users must click the “Delete” button that triggers a confirmation modal that asks for confirmation from the user if they are sure about the deletion process (Figure 35).

Figure 35 Delete system administrator modal dialog

In the next section, “Companies”, each company’s details, vessels and users are displayed, providing a structured approach to system wide company management (Figure 36).

Companies

CERTH IWW Shipping Services ▼

CERTH/HIT ▼

Test Company ▲

Action Options

Edit details Delete

Vessels

VESSEL NAME	LOCATED IN RIVER	
Matilda	Po	Show details
Roxanne	Po	Show details
Monika	Po	Show details
Bruchilda	Po	Show details
Edelweiss	Po	Show details

Users

USERNAME	FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	ROLE	
example@hotmail.com		S.	Company Ops	Show details Delete
test@certh.gr		T.	Company Admin	Show details Delete

+ Add User

+ Add a Company

Figure 36 Admin panel page, Companies section

The name of each company is shown as a collapsible header in an accordion panel. When the header is clicked, the company's information is displayed, along with tables for users and vessels and action options (Edit details, Delete). By clicking the "Edit details" (Figure 37) button the user is redirected to the My Company page for updating company information (e.g., name, registration, address). After the user has

completed updating the desired company information, they can click on the “Back to Admin Panel” button to return to the Admin Panel page (Figure 38).

Figure 37 Admin panel page, Companies section – Edit Details

Account Details			
Do you want to receive email Notifications ?			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> e-mail			
Alerts on river accidents			
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Po	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Seine	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moselle	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Vistula
My Company			
Name	<input type="text" value="Test Company"/>	Registration	<input type="text" value="123456"/>
Type	<input type="text" value="Shipping Company"/>		
Email	<input type="text" value="company@test.com"/>	Web Address	<input type="text" value="web-company.test.com"/>
Address	<input type="text" value="Somewhere 12"/>	Country	<input type="text" value="France"/>
Postal Code	<input type="text" value="11560"/>	City	<input type="text" value="Paris"/>
Change Password			
New Password	<input type="text"/>	Old Password	<input type="text"/>
<small>*Password must be at least 8 characters.</small>		<small>*Please confirm your old password.</small>	
<input type="button" value="Save Changes"/>		<input type="button" value="Back to Admin Panel"/>	

Figure 38 Admin panel page, redirection to My Company page

Next, is the “Delete” button which triggers a deletion confirmation modal dialog to remove the company (Figure 39).

Figure 39 Admin panel page, Companies section – Delete

Each company’s accordion element includes a “Vessels” table that presents the Company’s vessels with their name and the river inside which it carries out voyages. If no vessels exist, a “No records found” message appears. The “Show details” button shows detailed vessel information (Figure 40).

Vessels

VESSEL NAME	LOCATED IN RIVER	
Matilda	Po	Show details
Roxanne	Po	Show details
Monika	Po	Show details
Bruchilda	Po	Show details
Edelweiss	Po	Show details

Figure 40 Admin panel page, Companies section - Vessels

Vessel Details

Vessel Matilda

Nominal information for the vessel

Vessel Information

Vessel capacity is **TEU** when carrying **Containers**, **Tonnes** when carrying bulk cargo, m³ when carrying **liquid cargo**.

Basic Information

Name:	Matilda
Registration:	ABC-2211
Class:	Class III
River:	Po
Capacity:	50 TEU

Technical Specifications

Vessel Length:	80 m
Vessel Max Beam:	8.2 m
Vessel Draught:	2.5 m
Vessel Height:	5 m
Vessel Displacement:	1000 Tonnes

Past Trips

DEPARTURE PORT	DESTINATION PORT	DEPARTURE DATE-TIME	DESTINATION DATE-TIME	SPEED	TRIP HEIGHT	TRIP DRAUGHT	VESSEL CARGO
Porto di Chioggia	Porto di Cremona	2024-02-22 14:59:00	2024-02-23 15:00:00	10	4.7	2.5	50
Porto di Cremona	Porto di Chioggia	2024-02-02 14:59:00	2024-02-03 15:00:00	10	5	2.5	50
Porto di Cremona	Porto di Chioggia	2024-05-01 10:00:00	2024-05-02 18:09:21	10	5	2.5	50
Porto di Cremona	Porto di Chioggia	2024-05-01 11:37:00	2024-05-02 19:46:21	10	5	2.5	50
Porto di Cremona	Porto di Chioggia	2024-09-20 05:00:00	2024-09-21 18:50:56	10	5	2.5	50

X Close

Figure 41 Admin panel page, Companies section – Show vessel details

Moreover, there is the Companies “Users” table that lists their First Name, Last Name, and Role. If no users exist, a “No records found. Please add a User!” message appears. The Show details button redirects to a user details page (Figure 42), and the Delete button triggers a confirmation modal.

Users

USERNAME	FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	ROLE	
example@hotmail.com	Example	S.	Company Ops	<a>Show details <a>Delete
test@certh.gr	Test	T.	Company Admin	<a>Show details <a>Delete

+ Add User

Figure 42 Admin panel page, Companies section – Users

Profile Information

E

Example S.
Company Ops

• User Information

Basic Information

Full Name: Example S.

Company: Test Company

Role: Company Ops

Contact Details

Email: example@hotmail.com

Registered: 1 year ago

X Close

Figure 43 Admin panel page, Companies section – Show user details

To add a user, the “Add User” button is used that redirects to a user creation page where the user can fill out the required fields of Personal Details (First Name, Last Name and Email Address) and Account Security (Password, Confirm Password and Role (Company Admin or Company Ops) and then click the “+ Create User” button (Figure 44).

Add New User

Create New Account

Fill in the form below to create a new user

- User Information

Personal Details

First Name

Last Name

Email Address

Account Security

Password

Confirm Password

Role

Define Role
Company Admin
Company Ops

Figure 44 Admin panel page, Companies section – Create user

Additionally, the admin can “Add a Company” through this button, located below the Companies section. It redirects to a creation page for new companies. There, the admin must complete the necessary fields of Basic Information (Company Details (Name, Type and Registration) and Contact Information (Email Address and Web Address) and Location Information (Address Details (Country, City, Postal Code and Physical Address)) and then click the “Create” button to create the new company (Figure 46).

Figure 45 Admin panel page, Companies section – Add Company

Add Company

Create New Company
Enter company details below

- Basic Information**

Company Details

Name:

Type:

Registration:

Contact Information

Email Address:

Web Address:

- Location Information**

Address Details

Country:

City: **Physical Address:**

Figure 46 Add Company page

Finally, the last section of the Admin Panel is the “Stakeholders” section, which allows system administrators to manage stakeholder accounts, which may represent external or non-administrative users. Stakeholders are listed by username, first name, and last name in a table. A “No records found” message appears if there are no stakeholders. The admin can view the information of a stakeholder and delete it (Figure 47). When creating a new stakeholder, the admin must fill out the mandatory fields of Personal Details (First and Last Name and the Email Address) and the Account Security (Password and Confirm Password) (Figure 48).

USERNAME	FIRST NAME	LAST NAME	
@gmail.com	Victor		Show details Delete
@lgi.earth	Céline		Show details Delete
@ug.edu.pl	Jakub		Show details Delete
@gmail.com	Areti		Show details Delete
example2@gmail.com	Example2	Test2	Show details Delete

[+ Add a Stakeholder](#)

Figure 47 Admin panel page, Stakeholders section

Profile Information

E

Example2 Test2
Stakeholder

• Stakeholder Information

Personal Details

- 👤 First Name: Example2
- 👤 Last Name: Test2
- 🌍 Country: —
- 👔 Job Title: —
- 🗣️ Language: —

Contact & Address

- ☎️ Telephone: —
- 🏠 Street & No.: —
- 📮 Postal Code: —
- 🗺️ Municipality: —
- 📅 Registered: 7 minutes ago

✕ Close

Figure 48 Admin panel page, Stakeholders section – Show details

Add New User

Create New Account
Fill in the form below to create a new user

• **User Information**

Personal Details

First Name
First name

Last Name
Last name

Email Address
user@gmail.com

Account Security

Password
Password

Confirm Password
Confirm password

+ Create User X Cancel

Figure 49 Admin panel page, Stakeholders section – Create user

7.4. Accessibility remarks

User Interface (UI) Design refers to the visual layout and interactive components (buttons, forms, menus, feedback, navigation) of a software system, designed to make the interaction easy to understand, efficient, and visually appealing. In web application development, UI Design is crucial because:

- A well-designed UI has a direct impact on usability, making complex web applications easier to learn, navigate, and operate and therefore more successful [14].
- It ensures there is consistent User Experience (UX), making tasks easier for users, reducing errors, and minimizing drop-off rates.
- Promotes accessibility by enabling individuals with special needs such as visual, motor, cognitive impairments, and color blindness to effectively use the application. This is increasingly becoming a mandatory requirement across the EU and internationally [15].
- Good UI Design also improves performance metrics: faster task completion, reduced error rates, increased satisfaction, even better Search engine Optimization (SEO) and lower maintenance costs [16].

Under the European Accessibility Act (EAA, 2019/882) and the earlier Web Accessibility Directive (2016/2102), public and many commercial web applications must comply with digital accessibility

standards. The EAA, often enforced through EN301-549, that includes WCAG 2.1 AA requirements and mandates compliance by June 2025 for services provided in the EU [17] [18].

These guidelines are structured around the POUR principles:

- Perceivable: All content must be perceivable (e.g., alt-text for images, sufficient contrast) [19].
- Operable: Keyboard usability and content adaptability are essential for the interface [20].
- Understandable: Language and controls must be clearly defined [19].
- Robust: Content must function consistently across assistive technologies and devices [19].

Digital accessibility is also a legal and design priority beyond the EU:

- Under the 2018 accessible Regulations, the UK requires WCAG 2.1 AA and accessible declarations for public websites and apps [21].
- Through Section 508 and the ADA, the US mandates accessibility, requiring WCAG 2.1 AA for internal and public federal services [22].
- WCAG 2.1 is also used by nations like India using GIGW rules [23].

The SCMS platform has been designed with a strong emphasis on thoughtful UI design, aligned with international accessibility principles and inclusive design practices.

Color and contrast are fundamental to inclusive design, especially for users with visual impairments or color vision deficiencies. SCMS applies high-contrast color schemes, redundant visual cues, and clear feedback mechanisms to ensure that all users can perceive and interact with interface elements reliably and comfortably.

- The platform uses deep blue buttons with white text (e.g., “Find Alerts”, “Register”, “Select River”), providing strong contrast on light-gray background. This ensures readability for users with low vision or colour vision deficiency. Tools like Web AIM Contrast Checker confirm that these combinations exceed the minimum 4.5:1 contrast ratio required for body text under WCAG 2.1 AA.
- When a user selects a river (e.g., “PO”), the selection is indicated by both colour change and border styling, providing redundant visual cues. This is important for users who are unable to perceive colour or rely on screen magnifiers, and it also ensures visibility in various lighting conditions, including both indoor and outdoor environments.
- In alert or error states, such as the “No alerts found” message, the system uses bold red text with icons and toast components, making status updates are visually prominent and compliant with accessibility standards.

Form design plays a critical role in accessibility, particularly for users with cognitive disabilities, dyslexia, or memory challenges. SCMS structures its forms with consistent labeling, semantic HTML, and inclusive interaction patterns to support clarity, predictability, and assistive technology compatibility.

- Labels, input boxes, and field validation cues are all positioned near the top of input forms, which have a standard design. This layout supports users with cognitive disabilities and dyslexia who benefit from clarity and predictable structure.

- Required fields are marked with asterisks ("*"), and placeholders are descriptive (e.g., "Enter your email"). Field labels remain visible during input, avoiding the common issue of disappearing labels, which can hinder users with short-term memory challenges.
- As a best practice from modern inclusive design systems, the 'Show/Hide password' toggle icon is keyboard-accessible and incorporates ARIA-labeling (aria-label="Toggle password visibility"), which enhances usability and screen reader accessibility.
- The usage of suitable semantic HTML elements (<label>, <input>, and <button>) in all form components guarantees screen reader compatibility and semantic clarity.

Keyboard accessibility is essential for users who rely on non-mouse input methods. SCMS ensures that all interactive components are fully navigable via keyboard, with logical tab order, visible focus indicators, and ARIA-compliant controls that maintain usability and flow without interruption.

- The SCMS site contains fully keyboard-navigable forms and buttons, with visible focus indicators (typically blue or green) during tabbing. This is a key WCAG success criterion for operable interfaces.
- According to ARIA guidelines for interactive components, dropdown menus and buttons (such as river selection and alert period) can be interacted with using arrow keys and Enter.
- In contrast to inaccessible popups, which might interrupt focus or block screen readers, modal dialogues and feedback messages (toasts) are non-intrusive and provide continuous navigation without disrupting the flow.

A clear and semantic content structure enhances navigation for all users, especially those using screen readers. SCMS organizes its interface using numbered steps, meaningful headings and concise guidance cues to support task completion and reduce cognitive load.

- Numbered sections are used inside the pages ("Step 1: Select River"), making it easier for all users to browse the website, using screen readers like NonVisual Desktop Access (NVDA) or Job Access with Speech (JAWS), which rely on heading hierarchies and landmarks.
- Semantically coding each section's header with HTML5 headings (<h2>, <h3>) enables assistive devices to scan text effectively, a practice recommended by both W3C and GOV.UK.
- Informational cues (e.g., "Select message sender") provide users with brief but task-relevant guidance, avoiding cognitive overload.

Accessibility must extend across devices and input methods. SCMS is designed to be fully responsive, adapting its layout and interaction patterns to mobile screens and touch interfaces. This enables usability for users on smartphones and tablets, including those with motor impairments or limited dexterity.

- The SCMS layout adapts perfectly to mobile devices. On smaller screens, elements stack vertically and resize appropriately to maintain usability.
- Menus, modals, and inputs are touch-friendly requiring no precision gestures and supporting users with motor impairments and ensuring accessibility across devices.

8. Challenges & risk mitigation

8.1. Data gathering & digitalization

Throughout the development and deployment of the SCMS platform within the CRISTAL project, significant challenges were encountered in sourcing, digitizing, and structuring the data required to support real-time and forecasted navigability alerts. These challenges were consistent across all pilot implementations, Italian, French, and Polish and stemmed from both technical and logistical constraints.

One of the primary difficulties was the limited availability of live operational data. Much of the data used during the pilots was either mock or test data, which, while useful for demonstrating functionality, lacked the dynamic variability and reliability of real-world conditions. This limitation affected the accuracy and responsiveness of the alerting services, particularly in scenarios requiring up-to-date environmental or infrastructure status like the Disruption Impact Estimation and the Corridor Observatory services.

Additionally, the process of digitizing legacy data sources and transforming them into structured formats such as JSON proved to be complex and time-consuming. Many of the original data sources were not designed for digital interoperability, requiring manual extraction, formatting, and validation before they could be integrated into the SCMS via REST APIs. This was especially evident in cases where data originated from regional authorities or older monitoring systems, which lacked standardized output formats or consistent update schedules. In some cases, full digitization could not be completed, so semi-dynamic data updates methods were employed to make this kind of data available to the SCMS platform.

Despite these challenges, each pilot made substantial progress in establishing pipelines for structured data ingestion. In Italy, NtS and water level forecasts were digitized. In France smart buoy telemetry was integrated to monitor flood risks. In Poland, smart buoys and semi-dynamic document-based communications with local authorities provided a foundation for alert generation. However, the reliance on semi-automated or manual data sourcing methods highlighted the need for more robust, scalable, and interoperable data infrastructures to support future deployments.

Furthermore, as already discussed in section 3.1, due to the absence of structured and accessible booking data across transport modes, implementing mode-free booking was not viable. At present, users must manually consult external sources for transport schedules and availability in pilot regions. While this limits automation, it still supports informed decision-making. Future SCMS versions could enable seamless booking by integrating open APIs, real-time data feeds, or establishing data-sharing agreements with mobility providers.

Ultimately, these experiences underscore the importance of investing in data standardization, real-time sourcing capabilities and digital transformation of legacy systems to ensure the long-term viability and scalability of SCMS-like platforms in IWW and multimodal transport and logistics environments.

8.2. Software development

The development of the SCMS platform within the CRISTAL project entails a complex set of coding and integration challenges. These include managing complex geospatial data in a WebGIS-like interface with dynamic filtering and visualization tools, harmonizing diverse and often inconsistent JSON formats from a wide array of data providers, ranging from REST APIs and legacy systems to semi-dynamic document-based sources and implementing standardization pipelines to ensure consistent ingestion. The system orchestrates both push-based REST API endpoints and pull-based Laravel Console Commands (cronjobs), each requiring careful coordination with third-party systems' operational rhythms and data availability patterns. This is further complicated by the asynchronous nature of data flows and the limited initial datasets available for feature prototyping and validation.

Together, these challenges demand a resilient, modular and scalable backend architecture capable of adapting to evolving data landscapes and supporting operational decision-making across diverse IWW contexts. Equally important are the frontend-UI development requirements, which must accommodate dynamic geospatial rendering, responsive filtering mechanisms and real-time data visualization. The UI layer needs to be tightly coupled with backend logic to handle asynchronous updates, gracefully manage incomplete or delayed datasets and offer intuitive user interactions that reflect the complexity of multimodal transport planning.

9. Conclusions

This deliverable has presented the results of the work undertaken to implement the requirements and specifications of the **Synchromodal Corridor Management System (SCMS)** as defined in Deliverable 3.1 at the initial stage of the project. The SCMS constitutes a strategic tool designed to support the overarching objectives of the CRISTAL project, notably the enhancement of reliability, resilience and attractiveness of inland waterway transport systems. Particular focus has been placed on integrating rivers that are not part of the well-established networks of Northern Europe, acknowledging that these waterways play a vital role in achieving the European Union's climate and transport ambitions, as articulated in the European Green Deal and the Sustainable and Smart Mobility Strategy, in alignment with the objectives of the Paris Agreement.

Throughout the project, continuous engagement with pilot site partners, coupled with iterative development cycles, allowed the functionalities initially described in D3.1 to be refined in accordance with the practical requirements and available data sources of the pilot sites. Despite necessary adjustments to accommodate site-specific needs, all core functionalities, including the Early Detection and Information System, the Disruption Impact Estimation tool and the Action Toolbox of Services, were successfully implemented as originally planned. The system's architecture was designed with modularity, interoperability, and standardization at its core, in alignment with the FENIX classification of digital services. This ensures that the SCMS is not only fully operational and aligned with project objectives but also scalable, adaptable, and capable of integrating additional services and data sources in the future, establishing a future-proof platform with significant potential for wider deployment.

The deployment of the SCMS in the pilot sites was not without challenges. In the less digitally mature rivers, early project stages revealed limitations in data availability, digital infrastructure, navigability and connectivity to complementary transport modes, such as road and rail, which in turn affected the capacity to implement multimodal support for major disruptions. These challenges, while significant, were effectively addressed through the collaborative efforts of project partners, demonstrating the value of joint problem-solving in complex, multi-stakeholder contexts. As a result, the SCMS was successfully implemented and validated across all pilot sites, meeting the diverse requirements identified during the project.

Moreover, the iterative engagement with local transport ecosystems, facilitated through Living Lab events, provided a robust framework for validating the system's functionalities and assessing its practical impact. This process confirmed that the SCMS can substantially enhance operational decision-making, contributing to more resilient, reliable, and sustainable inland waterway transport. The successful realization of the system, despite the obstacles encountered, underscores the importance of collaborative approaches in addressing complex operational, technical and infrastructural challenges. Ultimately, the SCMS represents a significant step forward in digitalizing and modernizing inland waterway transport, offering a flexible and expandable platform capable of supporting both current operations and future developments in alignment with European transport and climate policy objectives.

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